

Designing Human-LLM Systems: A Review of Current State, Limitations, and Guidelines to Better Interaction

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Abstract. Large Language Models (LLMs) are profoundly transforming how humans create and interact with systems perceived as intelligent. While this field is highly active in human-computer interaction (HCI) research, the limitations of these interactions as well as the current state remain poorly identified or described, hindering their improvement and large-scale adoption. This paper aims to address these gaps by providing a new, concise analysis and guidelines structured along four axes: human, LLM, interface, and task. By compiling and mapping the challenges reported in the literature through an HCI lens, our research helps engineers, designers, and researchers assess factors that impact human-LLM interfaces, thereby meeting the growing demand for the successful integration of these technologies.

Keywords: Human-LLM Interaction; Mind-map; Limitations; Human factors; Review; Design Guidelines

1 Introduction

Every significant technological advancement has profoundly transformed the way humans use and interact with machines [1]. Recently, Large Language Models (LLMs) have undergone a major revolution, enabling humans to interact using natural language, significantly impacting a wide spectrum of disciplines, from social science to engineering [2]. This, consequently, has triggered a surge of interest and publication from the research community [2], [3], [4].

Nevertheless, despite the plethora of reviews available in the literature, main limitations persist in their procedure, as shown in Table 1, such as a lack of: 1- a human-computer interaction (HCI) analysis-oriented; 2-interdisciplinary approach; 3- a rigorous references corpus, and 4- a focus on human-LLM limitations. Indeed, some available reviews cite either a substantial proportion of preprint articles [2], [4], [5] or a high concentration of articles from the same source [6], [7]. This reliance may lead to the analysis of non-peer-reviewed content [8] and, in turn, potentially impact academic integrity [9].

Therefore, this research aims to contribute to the field by:

- Proposing a new and generalizable definition of human-LLM interaction.

- Gathering and synthesizing from diverse sources, including journals and conferences, a map of the current limitations of human-LLM interactions from an HCI perspective.
- Opening new areas and recommendations for designing LLM-based systems to meet the needs of successful growing integration.

This paper is organized following these sections: Method, to clarify terms and protocol employed; Results, where a mind map is presented to encapsulate main findings; Discussion, to detail and explain about each limit encountered; and Conclusion, to sum up this research.

Table 1. Screening of the current literature

Article	HCI-oriented	Interdisciplinary	Diversified and Trustworthy sources	Human-LLM Limitations detailed
[4]	X	✓	X	✓
[2]	X	✓	X	✓
[5]	X	X	X	X
[6]	✓	✓	X	X
[7]	✓	✓	X	X
[3]	X	X	✓	X
[10]	X	✓	X	X
[11]	X	✓	X	X
Our work	✓	✓	✓	✓

2 Method

In this section, the method is detailed to clarify terms and protocols.

2.1 Terminology clarification

LLMs are defined in the literature as models trained on large datasets with extensive parameter sets that process and perform high-level Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks [10], [11]. These features are related to training, model technology, and applications.

To provide a coherent analysis, a framework is required to draw out axes. In the current literature, only a few papers study human-LLM interaction. To the best of our knowledge, only Gao et al. [6] proposed a human-LLM taxonomy. Still, their depiction is diverse and possibly mixed across their different categories, failing to provide a clear framework for our research. Consequently, a generalizable definition is needed. To do so, we drew on the taxonomy of the hybrid intelligence field, which describes a hybrid intelligence system in terms of four elements: human, task, artificial intelligence, and collaboration mechanism [12], then adapted it to a human-LLM con-

text, namely, human, task, LLM, and human-LLM interface, as shown in Figure 1. Therefore, we defined human-LLM interaction as the synergy between humans and

Fig. 1. Human-LLM Interaction System

LLMs via an interface to complete a task. This new definition determines key elements in the human-LLM interaction, allowing us to identify limitations.

To remove any ambiguity, each limitation could be further defined as:

- Human: limitations related to human users or their behavior or cognition.
- Task: limitations inherent to the specific tasks or use cases.
- LLM: limitations inherent to the model or its capabilities.
- Human-LLM Interface: limitations arising from the interaction design or interface.

LLMs can handle a wide range of actions. To break them down, we derived the revised Bloom taxonomy, specifically from the cognitive processes, to keep the following actions [13]:

- “Understand” refers here to actions involving explanation, inferring, or summarizing.
- “Apply” actions related to executing procedures or implementation, such as coding.
- “Analyze” actions involving differentiating or attributing different elements.
- “Evaluate” actions requiring judgments based on criteria.
- “Create” as the process of combining various elements to produce something new, like generating ideas or planning.

Using these verb actions has the advantage of describing the tasks that LLMs overall perform, thereby avoiding subjective judgment, a limitation in previous reviews. Next, the tasks where LLMs and humans interact can be depicted as:

- Cognitive tasks, where humans and the LLM mainly exchange information, knowledge, or logical reasoning.
- Emotional tasks, where humans seek emotional support, an emotional exchange, or active listening.
- Physical/collaborative tasks, tasks where humans and the LLM (or a system controlled by the LLM) interact in a physical or simulated environment.

- Social tasks, where humans and the LLM simulate or facilitate social exchanges, often in a community or public context.
- Creative tasks, where humans and the LLM co-create content, ideas, or innovative solutions.

Regarding the interface, we distinguish chat and graphical user interface (GUI). Although chat interfaces are included in GUIs, they have historically been the main way to interact with LLMs; however, chat differs from the rest of the GUI, such as maps or software.

2.2 Database Screened

The database chosen is Scopus, provided by Elsevier, known for its reliability [14], where the following search: TITLE-ABS-KEY(("large language model" OR "large language models" OR "LLM") AND ("human-computer interaction" OR "human-machine interaction" OR "human factors" OR "ergonomics" OR "ergonomic issues" OR "usability" OR "user experience" OR "human-centered design" OR "human-robot interaction" OR "human-ai interaction")), has been run on the 08/09/2025 (day-month-year). The results have been downloaded in .csv format and exported to Excel for further analysis.

2.3 Selection Criteria

To ensure a high-quality selection of relevant articles, the following criteria were applied in the screening stage, including article information, title, and abstract:

- The article should be related to LLMs and their applications.
- The article should be relevant to the HCI field.
- The article should be peer-reviewed.

Additionally, a preference was applied to select papers from a diverse range of journals and conferences by checking, when possible, their 2024 scientific journal ranking in Scimago, a tool included in Scopus for comparing the impact of publications [15]. Next, the full texts of each article were analyzed to identify all clearly stated limitations. The entire process involved one person.

2.4 Procedure

To determine the number of articles included in this study, we followed a rule-of-thumb for conducting a mini-review of 60 articles. All articles were thoroughly reviewed and categorized into qualitative variables. The categories of LLM actions and interfaces can include multiple inputs due to the complex systems developed in the paper. Additionally, notes were made on every explicit limitation mentioned by the authors.

3 Results

A diverse range of papers [13-72] was analyzed. The main results were concatenated in Figure 2 to describe the current state situation of human-LLM interaction, and in Figure 3, a mind map of current limitations. Figure 2's features are described in detail in Table 2, and the flow's size allows an understanding of proportionality within one category and its connection with the others. Main articles included in this study were sourced from Q1 journals or impactful conferences.

Fig. 2. Sankey Diagram of the current state of human-LLM interaction. Some articles can have, at the same time, different LLMs' actions in multi-agent systems and different interfaces if several were implemented.

3.1 Current state of Human-LLM interaction

The current state of Human-LLM interaction can be described following these principal features:

- Despite a wide range of actions that LLMs could perform, their main actions are understanding-related actions, that is to say, in an information communication role for humans.
- Main tasks performed within human-LLM interactions are Cognitive tasks for instance, programming [44], [59], [60], problem resolution [18], [25], [43] or information seeking [40], [66], [74], and Physical/Collaborative tasks, mainly human robot assembly [47], [49], [58]. Physical/Collaborative tasks involve proportionally balanced LLMs' actions, as they usually employ a chain of LLM agents to deploy the overall system; for instance, in robot-collaborative tasks where LLMs control robots.
- Tasks within human-LLM interaction differ significantly between user types. Indeed, systems designed for expert users are more focused on Physical/Collaborative and Creative tasks, for instance, conducting research [38] or generating content under

a specific lens [17], [46]. In contrast, systems for general users with no expertise in the overall framework integration focus more on Social and Emotional tasks, for instance, through social chat [30], [36], [57].

- Interfaces differ a little bit between user types; however, the main ones for both are chat, robot, and GUI. Interfaces developed for general users tend to be more chat-like, while those for expert users are more focused on the GUI and offer deeper integration with existing specialized software.

Table 2. Summary of features extracted from articles included in our analysis.

Category	Features	Articles
Action	Analyze	[32], [43], [64], [66], [69]
	Apply	[18], [19], [29], [34], [35], [47], [66], [67], [71]
	Create	[20], [28], [38], [43], [44], [47], [49], [50], [51], [59], [60], [65], [67], [70], [75]
	Evaluate	[17], [22], [30], [36], [37], [48], [53], [64], [67], [75]
	Understand	[16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [30], [31], [33], [35], [37], [38], [39], [40], [41], [42], [45], [48], [49], [50], [52], [54], [55], [56], [57], [58], [60], [61], [62], [63], [65], [68], [70], [71], [72], [73], [74], [75]
Task	Cognitive	[18], [20], [21], [23], [24], [25], [27], [28], [29], [39], [40], [43], [44], [48], [51], [52], [53], [55], [56], [59], [60], [63], [66], [68], [71], [74], [75]
	Creative	[17], [38], [46]
	Emotional	[22], [26], [37], [45], [54], [61], [62]
	Physical/Collaborative	[19], [35], [47], [49], [58], [64], [65], [67], [69], [73]
	Social	[16], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34], [36], [41], [42], [50], [57], [70], [72]
User	Expert	[17], [18], [19], [20], [28], [31], [38], [43], [44], [47], [48], [49], [52], [53], [58], [65], [67], [68], [71], [75]
	General	[16], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [30], [32], [35], [36], [37], [39], [40], [41], [42], [45], [46], [50], [51], [54], [56], [57], [59], [61], [62], [63], [66], [69], [70], [72], [73], [74]
	Expert & General	[55], [60], [64]
Interface	Chat	[17], [18], [23], [24], [25], [30], [32], [34], [37], [38], [39], [40], [42], [44], [45], [48], [52], [54], [55], [56], [57], [60], [61], [63], [66], [71], [72], [75]
	Embody	[50], [63], [74]
	GUI	[19], [20], [22], [26], [27], [28], [31], [37], [45], [55], [56], [59], [64], [67]
	Robot	[16], [32], [35], [36], [47], [49], [58], [62], [63], [64], [65], [67], [69]
	Sensors	[21], [64], [67]
	VR Headset	[30], [41], [49]

Fig. 3. Mind map summarizing the limitations of Human-LLM interaction

To structure the analysis of the results, each limitation will be further explored and explained, as shown in Figure 3.

3.2 Limitations of Human - LLM interactions

Our analysis will involve examining reported challenges from each element's perspective: LLM, Human, Interface, and Task, then linking them to show how they affect human-LLM interaction.

3.2.1 LLM

The foundational element of human-LLM interaction is the LLM itself. However, this component introduces certain limitations. The following analysis will examine these challenges by focusing on the LLM's core components: model, output, data, and API.

LLM-Model

The uncontrollability of LLM is a critical problem that needs to be considered (Figure 2.i). This problem is reported as hallucination [20], [43], [67], and is defined in the

literature as the generation of contradiction in terms of logic, prompt, and knowledge [76]. For instance, this can emerge from the generation of fake information that misleads users and undermines their trust [44], [58], [75]. Moreover, it can be further fine-grained analyzed by defining it as the randomness behavior inherent to LLM’s output [17], [30], [37], [39], [39], [44], [47], [54], [60], [66], [67], even for easy tasks such as semantic analysis [17], or formatting results within a particular format [39]. This randomness could be a real challenge for chatbot systems [37], [39], [54], [66], especially for those created for mental well-being and self-reflection [37], [38], [54], compelling conceptors to define and monitor “harmful outputs” [54]. For example, it was reported that chatbot agents refused to accomplish the task given [44], showed aggressive [74] or deceptive behavior, including stating incorrect information with confidence [44], omitting instructions in the prompt [60], and offering a pseudo-emotional deceiving safety zone to users [45] (Figure 2.j). Establishing feedback mechanisms in LLM-based systems can help to prevent these undesired behaviors [67] by incorporating a human-in-the-loop control [37], [47], [60], [66], [68], integrating built-in tools [19], [54], [62], [65], or by fine-tuning models [43]. However, it is essential to note that implementing these safety constraints may come at the cost of LLM performance [22] and deteriorate users’ perceptions of LLM-based systems [50]. Additionally, several constraints have been reported concerning the fine-tuning of models [29], [34], [66], such as the challenge of assessing the impact of modifying different layers of an LLM [29]. Furthermore, a fine-tuned model may experience a decrease in performance [34], and selecting a specific fine-tuning approach can lock models into a particular task, potentially reducing the flexibility of LLM-based systems [66] (Figure 2.g).

Additionally, LLM models may exhibit weaknesses in specific capabilities, which can impact their performance (Figure 2.h). For example, one trivial limitation of LLM architecture was the lack of long-term memory. However, this limit was tackled by integrating past outputs into the prompt [74] or by developing adaptive approaches, such as dynamically establishing user profiles [45]. Then, some articles documented a lack of semantic understanding, including failing to understand users’ requests [75], handling cross-linguistic nuances [72], or technical terminology [18], [67]. A lack of contextual understanding was also highlighted in our analysis [35], [52], [64], [69], [70], [71], including companies contextual environment [52], human contextual input [70], [71], and a lack of understanding 3D real-world mechanisms [35], [64], [69]. This was extended to a lack of abstract understanding of mathematical concepts [25], [64], human cognition [25], [42], human emotion [62], [74], and human behavior [70]. These limitations affected the system’s performance and could even force users to repeat the same actions to achieve their intended tasks [75]. Regarding the conceptors of LLM-based systems, they had to explicitly handle data or develop built-in strategies to stabilize and monitor them [64], [67]. Surprisingly, only a few solutions were proposed in our corpus of articles to address these challenges.

The inherent bias of LLMs was a major concern raised in articles [25], [32], [37], [38], [42], [53], [70], [74], [75] (Figure 2.g). This primarily came from datasets that lack diversity [38], [53], [70]. In a human-LLM interaction context, it occurred as a confirmation bias, where LLM tended to omit fact that don’t align with its answer

[25], cultural bias, where several society mores were more emphasized [38], suggestion bias, where LLM leaded conversation [42], or political bias, where opinions were given about political leaders [74]. Using adequate prompting was reported as a solution to possibly mitigate these biases [74].

Another factor reported to be worth considering was prompt quality [34], [46], [53], [60], [73], [74] (Figure 2.g). This included problems such as overly long prompts due to many instructions [39], missing information attached [64], and information position [34]. On the contrary, it can be improved using few-shot prompting [43], [71] or prompt generators [46]. This aspect should be carefully considered, since it significantly impacts user engagement and perception of LLM-based systems [74].

Eventually, inference time was also reported in our corpus as a restraining factor in human-LLM interaction [21], [30], [35], [37], [49], [50], [75] (Figure 2.g). It was suggested that using smaller models could help reduce inference time [35] while keeping approximately the same level of performance for some tasks [33]. Inference time needs to be carefully evaluated, as it can affect user experience, for instance, making users bored [75].

LLM-Output

Several limitations arose from LLMs' outputs, including the synthetic nature of the answers and copyrighting interrogations (Figure 2.d). Indeed, synthetic answers were reported as a limitation for user experience. It designates together the fact that LLMs' outputs can be repetitive and verbose [50], [74], lacking human style, for instance in reasoning [25], [44], empathy [61], and cross-cultural linguistics speech [37], or lacking originality, tending to be standardized [38], [75]. Subsequently, a copyright issue was discussed, focusing on the extent to which generated content ought to be attributed to users [38]. This element needs to be rigorously assessed in LLM-based systems, as it can significantly affect long-term utilization [44].

LLM-Data

LLM models suffer from inherent limitations, such as outdated knowledge and the inability to deliver real-time updates [32], [44] (Figure 2.f). To address this, some articles have used approaches such as Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), which was also employed to provide domain-specific information [18], [20], [28], [49], [66], [72], or by fine-tuning models [22], [28]. Both approaches exhibited limitations related to data availability, such as imbalanced datasets [22], [28], task-specific data [49], or poorly structured data [72]. Moreover, LLM-based systems integrated with RAG faced additional challenges in human-LLM interaction, including the retrieval of incorrect information [48], missed relevant information [20], [72], and failures to correctly interpret retrieved data, even when the information itself was accurate [66], [72]. Therefore, these errors could profoundly affect human-LLM interaction and should be considered, especially in critical contexts as government-citizen policy communication [72].

LLM-API

When creating LLM-based systems, the question of whether to use an API becomes paramount for creators. Nevertheless, using API introduces new problems that should be taken into account, such as cost, privacy, security, availability, and model bias (Figure 2.e). As a matter of fact, costs stemming from API usage were quite discussed in our article corpus [31], [32], [37], [42], [44], [64], [65], [67], [71]. Indeed, it implies budget monitoring [37], and there was a real interrogation about the relevance of integrating LLMs via an external API call due to scalability constraints [31], [32], or simply it was economically less viable than other existing methods [37]. For instance, a cost of \$43 per worker per month was reported for one LLM-based system [65], casting doubt on its profitability for organizations. One solution mentioned to reduce cost was using locally LLMs [42], [65].

Another significant hindrance to employing API was privacy security [18], [20], [28], [32], [36], [37], [38], [48], [52] (Figure 2.e). In spite of open-source models being accessible, API models tend to be more performant [48]. This problem was still crucial for companies [17], [18], [20], possibly restraining LLM-based systems from complying with internal data regulations [18] or impacting the sustainability of these systems [37]. Not only was the use of local models [20], [36], [48] mentioned to address this problem, but also establishing data protection protocols such as data anonymization [28], data encryption [52], or manual erasure of sensitive and safeguarding user data from LLM providers [38], however, requiring a third-party reliance.

Then, the availability of the API was also a key concern reported [31], [32], [37], [44], [49], [62], [75] (Figure 2.e). This encompassed token limits [31], [37], [75], rate limitations, regional restrictions, and downtime [37], [44], [49]. This can introduce some delay in the system [62], therefore, impacting user experience. As mentioned before, using local models can be a solution to this problem, however, it requires adapted hardware [30], [48]. In both scenarios, a notable limitation was the scalability of LLM-based systems, when models are deployed on servers, referring to technical architectural constraints that prevent concurrent multi-user access [28].

3.3 Human

Human, as essential stakeholders, plays a crucial role in the human-LLM interaction framework. This section will detail the findings from our analysis.

Human skills were frequently mentioned as a limiting factor in human-LLM interaction [25], [38], [39], [52], [59], [68], [75] (Figure 2.m). Interestingly, it stemmed either from a lack of task-inherent skills [25], [59], or a lack of LLM literacy skills [25], [38], [52], [75]. For example, due to these issues, humans showed over-reliance on the LLM's output [25], [38], lost time by going down rabbit holes [59], disparaged advantages of LLM-based systems [39], or struggled to write proper prompts to achieve the desired results [25], [44], [52], [75]. The efficiency of human-LLM interaction relies predominantly on users' engagement [23] and understanding of LLM-based systems [52], highlighting a significant need to develop users' LLM literacy [25]. In addition, this could facilitate the adoption of such systems, as users with prior expertise tend to be more resistant to new technologies [68].

Limitations arising from human cognition were commonly observed in our article corpus [25], [27], [38], [39], [42], [45], [51], [52], [56], [57], [58], [59], [63], [66], [75] (Figure 2.l). This encompassed; automation bias [25], [38], [39], [59], a cognitive overreliance on system outputs [77]; framing bias [45], [57], a reality distortion based on how information is shown [78]; confirmation bias [51], judgment alignment on pre-existing personal beliefs [78]; appropriation bias [27], claiming credit for outputs achieved [79]; algorithmic bias induced by human [66], which is how the design of the algorithm, here LLM, deviates outputs; satisficing [42], where human adapts their behavior to disclose surface-level information [80]; anthropomorphism bias [45], [58], where human-traits are given to AI [81], in our context, LLM-based systems; psychological reactance [51], situations where human perceive a threat to their behavioral freedom [82] and; cognitive load [52], [56], [59], [63], [75], mental effort required to process and integrate information [83]. Concretely, these biases can jeopardize many aspects, including threatening human integrity [45], creativity [38], critical thinking [38], [39], opinions [57], learning [59], and emotions [45], [58], [59]. From a human-LLM interaction perspective, this could impact task performance [25], [38], [59], [66], user experience, perception, and trust of LLM-based systems [63], [75], or deviate from expected utilization [42]. Therefore, these biases should be actively considered in the design of LLM-based systems [51].

Next, human perception of the systems impacted the human-LLM interaction framework, including perceived usefulness, risks [23], satisfaction [23], [24], emotional dependence [45], workload, and performance expectations [24], [75] (Figure 2.k). This can directly affect technology adoption and application by exerting a detrimental impact on human willingness to use these systems [23], the technology trust [24], and by eliciting psychological distress [45]. As a result, a focus should be placed on improving user experience [24] and technology education [23] to tackle these issues.

Eventually, manipulative user intent was identified as a serious concern because it can breach LLM safety constraints, leading to unintended outputs (Figure 2.m). Therefore, manipulative user behaviors should be considered in the human-LLM interactions framework by implementing ethical frameworks to ensure regular and safe interactions [16], for example, with MoGu, an open-source defense strategy framework to detect subversive instructions [29].

3.4 Interface

The interface between human and LLM is a key component to examine, as it shapes how interaction occurs. In this section, limitations encountered in our corpus will be detailed.

Multi-modal interactions were identified as a limitation in human-LLM interaction (Figure 2.p). This was broken down into two categories: multi-modal outputs [46], [50], [55], [63], [66], [74], from the system to the human, and multi-modal inputs, from the human to the system [20], [30], [36], [75]. Regarding the multi-modal outputs, the modalities mentioned included text, voice, embodied [63], visual cues [50], diagrams [55], [66]. For the multi-modal input, it encompassed text, voice [75], dia-

grams [20], drawings [19], controllers [64], car sensors [21], and video [22]. Main problems included, the limited information flow in specific communication modalities, which can induce high cognitive load such as listening output [50], [63], voice output parameters that do not align with natural human features [74], misleading figures [55], and restrictions to text-based interactions, constraining human-LLM interaction in multimodal tasks [20], [75]. As a consequence, when designing a human-LLM interface, these issues should be reflected, as doing so can have positive impacts, for example, improving the user output comprehension with visualizations or visual cues [55], [66], increasing user trust [63], and enhancing user experience [30], [36]. However, poor design choices can adversely affect human-LLM interaction, as previously discussed.

Another factor that needs to be built into human-LLM interaction is transparency (Figure 2.p). Indeed, several transparencies were debated as reference transparency in LLM-outputs [44], [60], which is related to providing documentation used to produce the output; uncertainty communication [25], acknowledging ignorance about output elements and system capabilities [50], [58], [62], referring to communicate system skills. These problems impaired user experience [25], [44], elicited astonishment, induced idle time [58], and a mismatch between users' perceptions and the actual performance of LLM-based systems [50], [62]. So, this transparency-focused communication should be correctly integrated into the human-LLM interface to streamline its interaction.

Next, a consequent issue reported by articles was the communication style from machine, LLM and interface, to human [25], [31], [37], [39], [40], [41], [46], [55], [58], [59], [63], [74], [75] (Figure 2.o). This encompassed; the voicing style [25], [31], [46], [74], which referred to wanted the tone and conciseness by users; emotional speech [37], [74], [75], the integration of emotional feedback or features during the interaction; persona traits [41], the social LLM-based system tendency; modality format [63], referring to which channel to choose to communicate information; irrelevant artifact [55], pointing to elements which detrimentally affects user interaction and; interface proactive behavior to users, ranging from over-proactivity [39], [58], to a complete absence of proactivity [74]. These limitations could impact human-LLM interaction by affecting cognition engagement [39], decision-making [75], trust [40], [63], cognitive load [40], [59], [63], and technology adoption [41], [55], [74]. Therefore, conceptors should align with user preferences [40], select relevant features [55], and avoid information overflow [63] to avoid these issues.

This tuning to users' preferences was reported in participants' feedback from experiments [31], [39] (Figure 2.p). It can be further analyzed under the umbrella of personalization, encompassing the creation of user profiles across interactions [37], [42] to adapt the interface to users' knowledge, needs, and interests [55], [74]. As a result, users could leverage better LLM-based systems, reducing the need for explicit instructions in the prompt [39].

As previously mentioned, user experience plays a crucial role in human-LLM interaction (Figure 2.n). Across the corpus, we identified four main themes related which are controllability [25], [59], [66], [71], referring to the extent to which users can decide behavior of LLM-based system; usability [23], [25], [30], [63], [65], [66],

[74], which concerns the smoothness of the interaction; functionality [52], [59], [65], [74], relating to the features available within the system; and familiarity [63], which concerns how the interface presents features that are already known to users. Indeed, these parameters raised several challenges, for instance, the induction of adverse emotions due to limited user controllability [25]; questions of human responsibility and control over LLM hallucinations-outputs [71]; the alignment of desired features with user profiles [59]; the long system response time regarded from a systemic perspective [30]; the impossibility of using LLM-based systems due to disabilities [65]; and the willingness and trust to adopt technology [23], [63], [74]. Therefore, designers should reflect on these parameters to align with users' perspectives and ensure a satisfying user experience.

Finally, two last points identified were prompt entry [19], [71], and system security [49] (Figure 2.q). Prompt entry refers to the design and method of collecting user input in the interface. Indeed, some problems emerged, such as the possibility of entering incorrect information, which adversely affected system performance [19]. This raises the question of how constrained an interface should be designed to prevent ambiguous inputs, at the cost of impacting user experience, for example, with chatbots recurring, asking users to refine and explicit ambiguous information [71]. These design considerations are further associated with the challenge of establishing appropriate system behaviors in response to unforeseen events with potentially dangerous outcomes. Such considerations are particularly relevant in contexts where LLM-based systems control physical objects like robots [49]. Consequently, conceptors must assess potential failure states to implement effective responses.

3.5 Task

The task itself is the last component of human-LLM interaction, and several limitations emerged from it. Three primary sources mentioned were context constraint [22], [23], [63], [70], task requiring advanced human intelligence traits [26], [53], [67], and misuse [32], [33], [38]. Context constraint refers to two main limitations: situational and operational (Figure 2.b). The first stems from the situation itself, for instance, the context complexity, how much it requires attention from users [63], and context criticality [23], [70], how severe a risk can be on users, tending to elicit human anxiety and the need for human expertise in high-stakes environments [23], [70]. The second one, operational limitation, refers to complex and ambiguous tasks themselves [22], impacting system performance. For example, tasks requiring human intuition (Figure 2.a), as defined in hybrid intelligence concepts [84], showed weaknesses, such as those that require human empathy [26], common sense [53], and flexibility to handle unique sub-task features [67]. Consequently, we urge designers of human-LLM systems to consider the concepts of hybrid intelligence to question the very nature of these systems and their relevance.

Finally, the use of LLMs for questionable purposes was discussed in our corpus [32], [33], [38], such as spying [38], spreading misinformation [32], and political opinion meddling [33] (Figure 2.c). This represents a major ethical threat and a risk to public opinion if scandals involving human-LLM systems were to become public.

Such scandals could undermine the technology’s public reputation and adoption, leading people to perceive it more as a threat than an opportunity.

4 Guidelines

Through this review, we have identified takeaways and guidelines from all the analyzed articles, summarized in Figure 4. We advise designers and researchers developing LLM-based systems to weigh the added value of LLMs by comparing the targeted sub-tasks with the capabilities of LLMs and other existing solutions, to find the best technical trade-off, thus avoiding system oversizing and ensuring the consistent use of this technology, which should serve only as a tool available to address a specific problem or task. Furthermore, when justified and reasonable use is involved, several aspects must be considered regarding users, the interface, the LLM, and system security. We highlighted the limitations of human-machine interaction, their impact on users, and believe that successful integration depends on their considerations and mitigation strategies, such as the type of user, their skill levels, the system introduction, and management of potential system hallucination situations, which can be very sensitive in critical sectors and are relatively underexplored in the literature. Next, there is a reflection on the interface, or interfaces, that should result from a study that takes into account various factors of human-LLM interaction to achieve balance and informed choices, to identify potential weaknesses. Then, the technical dimension of LLMs must be understood to optimize their use, aligned with the deployment situation and the expectations of the targeted system. Finally, we strongly encourage researchers and creators of these systems to systematically assess risks, safety frameworks, and the operational context in which the systems operate, to ensure ethical use and respect for human integrity.

5 Discussion & Limitations

In this mini-review, we analyzed the current limitations of human-LLM interaction from several perspectives, ranging from technical to human factors, offering new insights into the field. We examined how and to what extent each component of human-LLM interaction influences the overall interaction holistically.

These limitations are crucial to assess as they significantly impact this interaction in several aspects, as discussed in previous sections. Nevertheless, the analysis retains the same common thread: the successful integration and implementation of these systems in society. To the best of our knowledge, this “out of the box” methodology represents a novel contribution to the field, with implications for every system that connects LLM and humans. Each limitation identified in this article suggests multiple avenues for reflection and research to enhance human-LLM interaction. For instance, technical improvements, such as advancements in an LLM’s understanding of data, could expand system capabilities, thereby enabling new forms of interaction. Similarly, exploring how and to what extent humans exhibit biased behaviors in specific

contexts could help identify scenarios where the use of such systems provides genuine added value.

We believe the future of human-LLM interaction is moving toward the complexification of systems, meaning LLMs will be part of, or even the backbone of, flexible, intelligent systems through a chain-of-agents. However, computing power will be a significant challenge hindering the deployment of the chain-of-agents architecture. In addition, currently, interacting with LLMs is mainly through a chat; nevertheless, future human-LLM systems could explore other, more natural and seamless alternatives. This is highly relevant, given that nowadays either sensor data can be integrated into a prompt or natively interpreted by multimodal-LLMs. So, further research is required to fully grasp these opportunities and create better human-LLM machines.

This research presents several limitations. Indeed, the analysis included only 60 articles, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings. However, since we widened the sources, we believe that this effect was mitigated. Another limitation is that a single person screened and read all analyzed articles, which may introduce reporting bias. Eventually, another database could have been included, such as Web of Science; however, it requires a license that we did not have during the investigation.

6 Conclusion

Through a fine-grained analysis, this review provides a new general definition of human-LLM interaction and crucial perspectives for designers of these systems, highlighting that the development of LLM-based systems requires an interdisciplinary approach and urging the scientific community to consider these aspects in their designs and utilization.

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